

The Biodiversity and Distribution of the Spiders of Nantucket Island, Massachusetts with Comments on Tuckernuck and Muskeget Island species.

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Andrew Mckenna-Foster and Cheryl Comeau Beaton
(Maria Mitchell Association, 4 Vestal St., Nantucket, MA 02554)

Abstract

On Nantucket Island, Massachusetts, we conducted spider biodiversity inventories in five permanent Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative 10 hectare plots representing four major island habitats: barrier beach and dunes, sandplain grasslands and coastal heathlands, scrub oak and pitch pine (represented by two plots), and hardwood forest. We collected 2,509 spiders (859 adults and 1,650 juveniles or immatures) representing 26 families and potentially 210 species. Within the plots we followed standard timed one hour collecting methods including aerial and ground collecting, beat sheeting, and sweep-netting. We also accepted spiders collected casually from anywhere on the island. Species richness curves suggest that our inventories are not complete for any of the sampled habitat types and that more collection is needed. The species composition is only 38% similar to a historical collection made by James H. Emerton in 1930. In addition, on the island of Tuckernuck, we collected 770 spiders (197 adults and 573 juveniles or immatures) representing 13 families and potentially 56 species. On Muskeget Island we collected 373 spiders (87 adults and 286 juveniles or immatures) representing 14 families and potentially 32 species.

Introduction

There are over 39,000 named species of spider in the world and this number grows each year (Ubick *et al* 2005). Spiders are an extremely important component in most ecological food webs as invertebrate predators and exist in every level of habitat from the soil to the tree canopy. Since spider diversity can be very high within a given area, the creation of an accurate species list can require collection in all seasons of the year for several years.

Nantucket is fortunate to have a historical list created between 1926 and 1929 by the noted arachnologist James H. Emerton and published by the Nantucket Maria Mitchell Association in 1930 (Emerton 1930). Emerton collected 170 named species and two unidentified species and states that the Nantucket spiders “are like those of Cape Cod and Martha’s Vineyard, with a rich salt-marsh and pond shore fauna and a scarcity of the forest species so common on the mainland” (Emerton 1930, pg. 162). Other surveys in Massachusetts have found similar numbers of species but only in very specific habitats. A very focused study investigating interactions between spiders and their prey in Eastern Massachusetts cranberry bogs collected 188 specimens encompassing 24 genera from eight families (Bardwell and Averill 1997). Along a rural mail delivery route in Mashpee, Massachusetts an eight-year study documented 199 species (Edwards and Edwards 1997). These studies under-represent the full diversity on the mainland. A more accurate estimation is an unpublished list by Robert Edwards that includes 530 species from 31 families on Cape Cod. The number of species on Nantucket is most likely between 200 and 400. Our goal during the 2006 summer was to update the island’s

species list by collecting as many species as possible and create species lists for the island's major habitats using comparable methods.

Collection Locations and Habitat Descriptions

We created five sample plots each within a permanently established Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative (NBI) Plot to best represent four major habitats on the island including 1) barrier beach and dunes, 2) sandplain grasslands and coastal heathlands, 3) scrub oak and pitch pine, and 4) hardwood forest. The Nantucket Conservation Foundation describes these habitat types along with salt marshes and ponds and bogs as the most commonly encountered habitats on the island (Nantucket Conservation Foundation website 2006). We chose the following named NBI Biodiversity Plots: Squam Swamp (hardwood forest), Massachusetts Audubon Society (hereafter Mass. Audubon) (sandplain grassland), Madequecham (scrub oak and pitch pine), Sheep Pond (shrubland, scrub oak and sandplain grassland), and Eel Point 2 (barrier beach and dunes) (Maps 1-6). Within each 10-hectare plot we delineated a 1-hectare square sample plot with flagging tape at each corner and in the middle of each side. Sampling was restricted within this square.

Below are habitat descriptions for our five 1-hectare plots.

Eel Point 2- Coastal dune habitat. The plot straddles the interface between protected inner dunes to the south with shrubs and small cranberry swales and outer dunes to the north sparsely covered in dune grass, rose and poison ivy. The predominant vegetation is dune grass, bayberry (*Myrica pensylvanica*), poison ivy (*Rhus radicans*), and wild cranberry (*Vaccinium oxycoccus*).

NE corner of plot NAD 27 UTM 19T 399899E 4572069N

Madequecham- Scrub oak and pitch pine on the east side of the island. The predominant plant species are scrub oak (*Quercus ilicifolia*), pitch pine (*Pinus rigida*), black huckleberry (*Gaylussacia baccata*), viburnum (*Viburnum dentatum*), bayberry (*Myrica pensylvanica*), and low-bush blueberry (*Vaccinium angustifolium*). This plot has a very dense shrub layer interrupted by a few small blueberry swales and grassy areas and a dirt road passes through the plot. About one third of the plot is covered by pine stands.

NW corner of plot NAD 27 UTM 19T 412210E 4567402N

Mass. Audubon property- Sandplain grassland/heathland. The predominant plant species are black huckleberry (*Gaylussacia baccata*), low-bush blueberry (*Vaccinium angustifolium*), several low grasses and scrub oak (*Quercus ilicifolia*). The plot is in an area with moderate elevation variation and contains large huckleberry clones, open grassy areas, and widely separated clumps of scrub oak each no more than three meters high.

SW corner of plot NAD 27 UTM 19T 417179E 4569885N

Sheep Pond- Shrubland, scrub oak, sandplain grassland, and pitch pine on the west side of the island. The predominant plant species are scrub oak (*Quercus ilicifolia*), black huckleberry (*Gaylussacia baccata*), low grasses, and one side of the plot is predominated by pitch pine (*Pinus rigida*). The oak is much denser here than at the Madequecham plot and the huckleberry clones are also smaller. There are several large ant mounds of the family Formicidae in the scrub oak areas. About one quarter of the plot is covered by pine. NE corner of plot NAD 27 UTM 19T 401300E 4568984N

Squam Swamp- Hardwood forest. The predominant plant species are 12-15 meter high tupelo trees (*Nyssa sylvatica*), red maple (*Acer rubrum*), sweetpepper bush (*Clethra alnifolia*), cinnamon fern (*Osmunda cinnamomea*), goldenrod (*Solidago sp.*), and poison ivy (*Rhus radicans*). During the early summer, approximately one-third of the plot contains shallow, standing water under the vegetation.

SW corner of plot NAD 27 UTM 19T 416087E 4574628N

Collection Methods

We logged a total of 80 collection hours, 69 of which were completed in the sample plots, 860 total trap nights, five litter samples, and many casually collected contributions. Twenty-seven collectors participated over the summer and several logged more than five hours of collecting time. All of the collectors were inexperienced.

Casual Collecting

Many people brought in spiders collected in their homes or on walks and we collected spiders opportunistically to represent as many species in the collection as possible. This type of collecting took place on all three islands.

Timed Collection Methods

We collected spiders following standardized procedures described by Coddington *et al.* (1991, 1996), Cushing (2004) and Scharff *et al.* (2003) who recommend timed aerial collecting, ground collecting, sweep netting and beat sheeting. We timed each of these methods for one hour. Aerial collecting required the capture of all spiders in vegetation and on webs from knee height to as high as one could reach. Ground collecting sampled vegetation and webs below knee height. Collectors completed a beating event by shaking a selected branch for three seconds over the sheet. A sweep-netting event was completed after five continuous sweeps through one patch of vegetation. Each collector used one of these methods following a straight transect line through a sample plot or other area for one hour without stopping. Transects varied in length ranging from 50 meters to 100 meters and were about one meter in width. Scharff *et al.* (2003) and Coddington (pers. comm. 2006) also suggest cryptic searching (i.e. looking under debris) as a fifth method to find spiders under logs or rocks. We did not include this method in our collection but depended on Berlese funnels and pitfalls to sample these spiders.

Within one collecting hour, we chose methods that would sample the habitat most effectively. For example, if a collector was following a transect through knee high grass she would collect using a sweep net or ground searching. During a collecting hour each collector used a different method. If there were more collectors than methods the extra collector would be assigned a method that either sampled a unique microhabitat or a method that was under-represented in the data set. Since all of the collectors were inexperienced, exceptions were made when a collector felt uncomfortable with a collecting method (e.g. ground searching in poison ivy).

Pitfalls and Berlese Funnels

Since there is large ground spider diversity and many individuals live in cryptic habitats under rocks, logs, and dead leaves we used pitfall traps and Berlese funnels to augment the ground collections. Due to time constraints we were only able to collect one litter sample from each site for the Berlese funnels. We collected one square meter of

leaf litter and distributed it into eight funnels 15 cm in diameter. If some of the litter did not fit into the funnels it was stored in a refrigerator at 7C and put into the funnels four days later. Arthropods were extracted for four days under four 60-watt bulbs and collected into cups containing 70% ethanol.

We set out five pitfall traps at each site at intervals of about 10 meters. Each trap consisted of an eight-ounce canning jar with a funnel hot-glued to the screw-on top. The trap was buried so the lip of the funnel was flush with ground level and was covered with half of a four gallon plastic temporary landscaping pot (cut longitudinally) to protect it from rain. We used propylene glycol mixed with ethanol in various concentrations in the traps. Robert Edwards (pers. comm. 2006) uses this design on Cape Cod for his collections. These pitfalls were set out at least three times during the summer for at least three days each (Table 1).

Pitfalls were open at each site for a total of at least 100 trap nights and several were open for over 200 trap nights from late June through early September (Table 1). The number of trap nights is inconsistent due to early problems with flooded traps. The collection was too inconsistent to provide useful statistics but was invaluable in collecting species.

We also set out five pitfall traps at 10-meter intervals in a burned area 150 meters south of the Mass. Audubon sample plot. This predominantly scrub oak area was burned during the spring of 2006. The traps were set twice in the late summer, once for four days (5Aug.-9Aug.) and once for seven days (23Aug.-30Aug.).

Tuckernuck and Muskeget Collecting Methods

We collected on Tuckernuck Island from 26 to 27 August 2006 (Map 7). Methods were identical to those used on Nantucket except we did not set up sample plots. Instead we focused collecting in three habitats: black oak (*Quercus sp.*) mesic forest, a wetland/tupelo (*Nyssa sylvatica*) grove, and an open sandplain grassland site. With three collectors we completed 12 collection hours using all four methods, took one litter sample, and logged 10 pitfall trap nights.

We used the same collecting protocol while collecting on Mukeget Island from 12 to 13 August. The island is approximately 0.6 sq. mi. and much of the land can be described as unprotected dune habitat predominated by poison ivy (*Rhus radicans*) and juniper (*Juniperus sp.*) (Map 8). There are several small ponds bisecting the island flowing north to south. A small salt marsh occupies the southwestern edge of the island. With four collectors we completed 12 collection hours using the four methods, took one litter sample, and logged 7 pitfall trap nights.

Data Analysis

We designed the collection process so our collections and methods could be accurately compared between the sample plots. Comparing the different collecting methods is useful in determining how effective and efficient the collection was. For this purpose, Coddington *et al.* (1996) suggests the use of a sampling intensity determined by dividing the number of specimens by the number of species. A survey should strive to have equal sampling intensity between all the collection methods so each niche of a habitat is represented equally in the collection. The desired intensity value increases as habitat diversity increases. Coddington *et al.* (1991) initially suggested a value of 10 for

a tropical forest. In a later study Scharff *et al.* (2003) suggested a value of 30 for a deciduous Northern European forest. A species richness curve is also useful in quantifying inventory completeness. The curve is a plot of the number of specimens collected versus the accumulated number of species. We used the software program Estimate S to generate richness curves as well as calculate a Sorensen similarity index for the plots (Colwell 2005).

Nantucket Results

We collected 2,509 spiders (859 adults and 1,650 juvenile or immature) representing 26 families on Nantucket and we identified 157 species (Appendix A). However, there are an additional 53 morphological species that have yet to be identified to species and are labeled “sp.” followed by a letter in Appendix A. They have been separated based on morphological differences and further work is needed to identify them. Therefore, there are potentially 210 species in the collection. The identifications have not been confirmed and a complete and accurate list will not be ready until the fall of 2007. The collection will be stored at the Harvard Museum of Comparative Zoology and a voucher collection will be incorporated into the Maria Mitchell Association’s Natural Science Museum entomology collection.

Of the 210 species, 144 were collected in the sample plots and were identified from 644 specimens. We captured 27 species at Eel Point 2, 70 species at Madequecham, 55 species at Mass. Audubon, 47 species at Sheep Pond, and 54 species at Squam Swamp (Appendix A). We collected 80 species during timed collections and 81 species in pitfall traps (Tables 1 and 2). Seventeen species were trapped in both pitfalls and captured by hand. Sixty-three of the 144 species were only captured by hand while 64 of the 144 species were only caught in pitfalls. Almost half of all the species captured were taken in pitfalls and this highlights the importance of pitfall trapping in this survey. Each Berlese funnel sample was counted as one hour of collection. The timed collections accounted for 47% (300/644 spiders) of the total number of adults captured in the plots and pitfalls made up 53% (344/644 adult spiders). Casual contributions make up the remaining third of the total collection of adult specimens.

Table 1. The five pitfall traps at each site were open periodically between late June and early September. Many sites had overlapping species but the total number of species caught from all the pitfalls combined was 81 species.

Site	Pitfall Trapping Interval					# Trap nights	# Spiders	# species
	1	2	3	4	5			
Eel Point	3 July-9 July	9 July.-17July	6 Aug.-10 Aug.	31 Aug-7 Sept		130	44	10
Madequecham	31 May-23 June	1 July-9 July	9 July-16 July	5 Aug- 9 Aug	24 Aug-31Aug	250	94	35
Mass. Audubon	5 June-14 June	5 July-9 July	9 July-15 July	5 Aug-9 Aug	23 Aug-30 Aug	150	78	29
Sheep Pond	9 July- 17 July	6 Aug-10 Aug	31 Aug-7 Sept			100	52	27
Squam Swamp	31 May-23 June	1 July-9 July	9 July- 16 July	5 Aug- 9 Aug	23 Aug-30 Aug	230	76	27
Totals						860	344	81

Table 2. Number of spiders and number of species captured in timed collections and in pitfalls

	# adults	# unique species	# shared species	Total # species/method
Timed Coll.	300	63	17	80
Pitfalls	344	64		81
Totals	644	127	144	-

Pitfalls located in the burned site near the Mass. Audubon plot were open for a total of 60 trap nights and caught 17 spiders representing four families: Linyphiidae (Sheetweb builders)(10), Lycosidae (Wolf spiders)(4), Thomisidae (Crab spiders)(2), and Unidentified (1). Only three of the spiders were adults. The data set is not large enough for analysis.

Neoscona arabesca was the most abundant spider in the whole collection with over 112 individuals. It was followed by another orb weaver, *Acanthepeira stellata* (67), a jumping spider *Hentzia palmarum* (45), an ant mimic *Castianeira longipalpa* (32), and a wolf spider *Schizocosa avida* (32).

Species composition at each site differed. *Neoscona arabesca* (orb weaver), *Castianeira longipalpa* (ant mimic) and *Ozyptila conspurcata* (crab spider) were the only fully identified species collected at all five sites. Seven species were shared between four of the sites and 10 were shared between three sites (Appendix A). These numbers may increase as the morphological species are identified. We calculated Sorensen indices to compare data from each plot since the index uses the presence or absence of species rather than abundance values to compare two collections (Table 3). These indices only include data from the timed collections because the number of pitfall trap nights was too inconsistent to allow comparison between sites. All the values are under 0.5 suggesting the sites are not very similar with each other (sites with the same composition would have a value of one). Taking the values relative to each other, the beach and dune plot shows little similarity with the other plots except with the sandplain grassland/heathland plot where it shows the strongest similarity of all the sites. The species composition at the sandplain grassland/heathland site shows little similarity with the hard wood forest and eastern scrub oak and pine plots. The eastern and western scrub oak and pine plots and are both most similar to each other and least similar to beach and dune habitat. The hardwood forest habitat is most similar to the scrub oak and pine plots. The Muskeget Island collection is most similar to the Nantucket sandplain grassland/heathland and coastal dune habitats.

Table 3. Sorensen similarity indices calculated with the software program Estimate S to compare the species compositions of our five collection plots and Muskeget Island (Colwell 2005). This index uses incidence data rather than abundance data to calculate a value between zero (dissimilar) and one (similar). This table represents similarities based on species collected during timed collections and not pitfall trapping. It does not represent the ground dwelling species composition as well as it does the climbing and web-building spiders.

Sorensen Similarity Indices, (1 = Same, 0 = Different)					
	Coastal Dune	East Scb Oak/Pine	Snd Pln grasslnd/heath	Muskeget Isl.	West Scb Oak/Pine
East Scb Oak/Pine	0.161	-	-	-	-
Snd Pln Grasslnd/heath	0.448	0.202	-	-	-
Muskeget Isl.	0.346	0.111	0.237	-	-
West Scb Oak/Pine	0.232	0.285	0.280	0.188	-
Hrd Wd Forest	0.083	0.205	0.072	0.034	0.244

Comparison with the Historical Collection

We captured 65 species that Emerton lists in his historical record (Appendix B). This is only 38% of Emerton's list and most of these species are the most common representatives of their family. There are probably several more corresponding species (especially among the Linyphiidae) that have not been identified in our collection.

Species of Note

We are currently working to determine the rarity of any identified species but there are two species that stand out for other reasons. A black widow (*Latrodectus mactans*) was captured by an electrician in 2000 in an electrical box on Mill Hill and another was found on the east edge of the town of Nantucket at the Stop & Shop on an unknown date. Both specimens are stored in the MMA collection. *L. mactans* is not native to Nantucket and was not found by Emerton. This species most likely came to the island on goods shipped from the mainland and their population is probably localized within the town of Nantucket. It is the only medically important species found. We found the introduced and very common species of sac spider (*Cheiracanthium mildei*) that some consider medically important but the evidence is scarce and its danger has been refuted (Vetter *et al.* 2006)

The other interesting species encountered is the cryptic mygalamorph spider *Sphodros niger* or the purse-web spider. These tarantulas are native to the northeast United States and eastern Canada. We trapped two males early in the summer, one at Squam Swamp (between 31 May and 23 June) and one at Sanford Farm (on 14 June). We did not trap any females. Both sexes of *S. niger* build a notoriously cryptic silken tube and rarely leave it so the true range is not well documented (Edwards and Edwards 1990). Specimens have been found as far west as Douglas Co, Kansas, as far north as Belleville, Ontario and as far south as Macon Co, North Carolina (Gertsch and Platnick 1980). Edwards and Edwards (1990) located several specimens in the southwest corner of Cape Cod.

Analysis of Timed Collecting Method

Our sampling intensity was 3.8 (300/80) and it ranged from 1.3 to 4 between the different methods (Table 4). We expected these low numbers because our focus was to collect as many species as possible from several habitats rather than collect every species from just one habitat.

Table 4 Sampling Intensity for each site and each method is found by dividing the number of adult spiders by the number of species. The total number of species including pitfall data and excluding shared species is the number of species represented by adult specimens.

	Coastal Dune	East Scb Oak/Pine	Snd Pln Grasslnd/heath	West Scb Oak/Pine	Hrd Wd Forest
Aerial					
# collected	2	30	12	32	3
# species	2	7	5	7	3
Samp. Intensity	1	4.3	2.4	4.6	1
Ground					
# collected	10	25	29	13	19
# species	7	15	14	9	9
Samp. Intensity	1.4	1.67	2.1	1.4	2.1
Beat					
# collected	5	23	8	8	31
# species	2	13	6	6	14
Samp. Intensity	2.5	1.8	1.3	1.3	2.2
Sweep net					
# collected	11	3	9	0	7
# species	7	3	3	0	3
Samp. Intensity	1.6	1	3	0	2.3
Berlese					
# collected	8	5	1	2	4
# species	2	3	1	1	3
Samp. Intensity	4	1.7	1	2	1.3
Totals					
# coll. Hrs.	12	14	14	14	15
Total # adults coll.	36	86	59	55	64
Total # species	14	36	21	20	25
Site Sample Intensity	2.6	2.4	2.8	2.8	2.6
# Adults/hr.	2.4	7.4	4.5	4	5.1
# species incl. pitfall data, excl. shared sp.	22	64	47	44	50

In terms of effectiveness, aerial collecting produced the highest number of spiders per hour but the lowest number of species per hour (Table 5). Beat sheeting produced the lowest number of specimens per hour but collected the highest number of species. A more useful comparison for estimating collection efficiency is how much overlap there is between the species captured by each method. Ideally, there would be very little overlap and abundance data would not be skewed by over-collection of one assemblage of spiders. Berlese funnel collection and aerial collection show the lowest number of shared species and beat sheeting shares the most (Table 5). Between two and eight species are shared among the other methods and the percentage varies depending on how many species were collected with each method.

Table 5. Comparisons in the effectiveness of hand collection methods.

	# of shared species
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	# Specimens	# Species	# Collection hrs	Specimens per hour	Species per hour	Berlese	Ground	Aerial	Beat	Sweep net
Berlese	20	7	5	4	1.4	-	1 (14%)	0	1 (14%)	1 (14%)
Ground	96	39	28	3.4	1.4	1 (2.6%)	-	6 (15%)	8 (21%)	5 (13%)
Aerial	79	18	14	5.6	1.3	0	6 (33%)	-	6 (33%)	2 (11%)
Beat	75	30	14	3.1	2.1	1 (3.3%)	8 (27%)	6 (20%)	-	8 (27%)
Sweep net	30	14	8	4	1.8	1 (5.8%)	5 (36%)	2 (14%)	8 (57%)	-
Total	300	80	69	4.3	1.2	3	20	14	23	16

We collected for almost twice as many hours at night than in the day and there is no indication as to whether one time was more successful than any other (Table 6). The number of species captured at night is not disproportionately large compared to the number caught in the day because the different collection efforts (i.e. collection hours) are not comparable. The night collection and day collection share 19 species.

Table 6 Comparison of night and day collections of adult spiders.

	# of species	# of coll. hours	# of unique species	# of shared species
Day	38	26	19	19
Night	55	43	36	
Total	74	69	55	

Species Richness Curves

We did not have large enough datasets from our plots to create full richness curves and we knew from the start that our inventory would not be statistically complete. The curves for the western scrub oak and pine plot (Sheep Pond) are useful in proving this point and since the curves for the other sites are all very similar, they are not shown (Figure 1). We created the curves with Estimate S software (Colwell 2005). Ideally, the estimated and observed curves should level out relatively near each other at some asymptote (Scharff *et al.* 2003). The asymptote is the estimated number of species. The estimated curves are created by the software using several different estimation methods and 50 randomizations of the observed data.

The western scrub oak and pine site was the only site where an estimator began leveling off. The final observed number of species, excluding pitfall data, is 20 but the estimated curves are all above 25 and only the Chao 1 estimator begins to level off around 41 species. The other estimators do not show any sign of an asymptote. Additionally, in a complete survey, the number of species represented by two specimens (doubletons) should be higher than the number represented by one specimen (singletons) and both should level off and decline. Neither of these curves in Figure 1 follows this pattern. The number of singletons, and thus the number of new species captured with each new effort, is above the doubletons and increasing. This suggests there are more species that have not yet been caught.

Figure 1. Species richness curves for the western scrub oak and pine sample plot using Estimate S software (Colwell 2005). This figure does not include pitfall data.

Tuckernuck and Muskeget Results

On Tuckernuck we collected 770 (197 adults and 573 juveniles or immatures) spiders representing 13 families and 35 named species and 21 unnamed morphological species for a total of 56 possible species (Appendix C). Six of these species were not captured on Nantucket and there are an additional nine morphological species that have not been found on Nantucket. We found an abundance of one species of native tarantula (*Sphodros rufipes*) in two areas on the island separated by about one mile. We estimated there were 40-50 tubes within a 100 m² area.

On Muskeget Island we collected 373 (87 adults and 286 juveniles or immatures) spiders representing 14 families and 27 species and 5 unnamed morphological species for a total of 32 possible species (Appendix D). Four of the species were not caught on Nantucket.

Discussion

In addition to starting species lists for Tuckernuck and Muskeget, we were successful in creating an updated species list for Nantucket and collecting baseline species composition data for four major habitat types on the island. The sampling intensities for each site (Table 4) and species area curves (Figure 1) both suggest that our inventories in the plots are not complete and that there are more species to be found. We also did not find many of the same species Emerton recorded in the late 1920's but this is probably due to different collection locations, different collection methods, and changes in species composition. For example, Emerton found 45 species in the Creeks area east of the town harbor and this was not one of our collection areas. We instead decided to focus on interior island habitats and leave salt marsh habitat for a future study. More collecting is needed, especially in mature hardwood and salt marsh habitats.

The collection provides enough information on species composition and species diversity for comparison between the sites. Based on our analysis, the barrier beach and dune habitat and sandplain grassland/heathland habitat are both more similar to each other than to any of the other habitats. Similarity in habitat structure is one possible reason for this. Both habitats have large areas of low vegetation and scattered shrubs, which support similar spider guilds. Neither have pine trees or dense ground litter. However, this information is misleading because we were not able to include pitfall data in the similarity index. The beach and dune sandy substrate probably supports a much different ground spider community than the well-defined turf present in the sandplain grassland/heathland. With pitfall data the similarity between the two sites would decrease. Muskeget Island spider composition is very similar to that of the Nantucket barrier beach and dune habitat. This is expected as the habitats are very similar.

The other habitats all are least similar to the barrier beach and dune habitat and this is expected since all three have dense leaf litter, tall trees and lack large areas of open ground. After the beach and dune habitat, the sandplain grassland/heathland is most similar to the western scrub oak and pine habitat, which shares many dominant plant species and has remnants of sandplain grassland. As expected, the western and eastern scrub oak and pine habitats are relatively similar to each other.

The timed collections were consistent between sites in number of spiders collected and sampling intensity suggesting that our collection accurately represents the relative abundances of spider guilds (Table 4). Future studies should use all the collection methods and skew the effort slightly toward ground collecting. Ground collecting routinely collected more species than other methods and this larger species population requires more collecting hours to obtain a comparable sampling intensity (Table 4). Other methods are just as important. Beat sheeting and ground collecting both showed the most overlap in collected species with other collection methods. Beat sheeting samples for spiders that are hard to find during aerial searches but it also collects many of the easily seen spiders (except for some of those in webs). Beat sheeting captured more species than aerial searching (Table 5). Ground collecting samples spiders below knee height but this often includes spiders that build webs at all levels of a habitat and are also collected by aerial collection, beat sheeting and sweep netting. More specific guidelines may focus ground collectors and reduce species overlap. These guidelines should encompass spider webs that span above and below knee height and should suggest collectors complete the collection by crawling as much as possible rather than walking.

Despite the inexperience of all the collectors, none of the collection methods, except sweep-netting with beat sheeting, shared more than 40% of the collected species and most were under 20% (Table 5). This suggests the methods were easy for beginners to learn and successful in capturing the targeted spider guild. It also suggests that relatively accurate spider surveys can be completed with inexperienced collectors.

Further collection is needed on both Tuckernuck and Muskeget Island. We were only able to collect once during the summer at each island and missed species that mature in early summer or in late fall. With more intensive collections we will be able to compare the spider fauna of all three islands.

On Tuckernuck we focused on dry black oak (*Quercus sp.*) forest habitat, wet bog and tupelo grove habitat, and open grassland areas. We did not collect around salt

marshes and other microhabitats. However, we located at least 50 silk tubes of *Sphodros rufipes*. None of tubes were under the low grass and pine needle layer as Edwards and Edwards (1990) suggest of the widespread yet extremely cryptic *Sphodros niger*. *S. rufipes* is a more southern species and has not been caught on Nantucket.

On Muskeget, we collected in the predominant dune/juniper habitat and small marsh/wetland habitat and while these are the two main habitats they do not fully represent the island. The ground spider fauna is under represented and several nights of pitfalling is needed.

Future Work

Creation of stable species richness curves based on thorough collections from the major habitats on Nantucket Island is an important next step. This will increase our knowledge of spider biodiversity and provide statistically comparable species estimates. Ultimately we would like to assemble comparable species lists for Tuckernuck and Muskeget as well. The sandplain grassland and heathland habitat should be a first priority based on its unique abundance on Nantucket, Tuckernuck and Martha's Vineyard (Nantucket Conservation Foundation website, 2006). Scrub oak and pitch pine habitat should also have a high priority as it grows in over sandplain grassland. Species richness curves for both of these habitats would address the question of whether changing habitat structure has an impact on the local spider populations. The scrub oak and pitch pines offer more structure for spiders and different prey types. Non-native spiders may prefer one habitat over the other. Future work could ask the simple question: does the native and non-native spider assemblage change significantly between sandplain grassland and scrub oak and pine?

The species richness curves can also be used as management tools. Knowing how diverse habitats are relative to each other can be used as a way to maximize the abundance of rare or target species within a conserved area by varying the proportions of several habitats within that area (Tjorve 2002). Burning and mowing are two ways to vary the proportions of two neighboring habitats and are common practices on Nantucket.

Another future project should investigate the range and natural history of *Sphodros niger* on Nantucket and the *Sphodros rufipes* on Tuckernuck. Since males of *S. niger* wander in early summer to look for females, pitfall traps should be set in the first two weeks of June in Squam Swamp and Sanford Farm on Nantucket. Night searches may yield live males as well. On Tuckernuck pitfall traps should be set around the same time to look for *S. niger* and set again in early July when males of *S. rufipes* have been seen wandering (Creighton 2007).

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Appendix A. Nantucket Species List
 (imm. = immature, penult. = penultimate or juvenile)

		Dune	Scrb Oak/Pine East	Snd pln grs land/heath	Scrb Oak/Pine West	Hrd Wd Forrest	Other Nantucket Location
Family							
Genus	species						
Agelenidae (Funnelweb weavers)							
Agelenopsis	emertoni		1 ♂		2 ♂		
Agelenopsis	potteri	3 ♀	2 ♀ 1 ♂		2 ♀	1 ♂	7 ♀
Tegenaria	domestica						1 ♂
Amaurobiidae							
Amaurobius	Ferox						3 ♀
Coras	sp. A						1 ♀
Anyphaenidae (Running spiders)							
Arachosia	cubana						1 imm.
Hibana	sp. A	1 ♀		2 ♀			
Araneidae (Orb weavers)							
Acanthepeira	stellata	5 imm.		2 ♀			1 ♀
Araneus	alboventris			1 ♀			
Araneus	bicentenarius						1 penult. ♂
Araneus	bivittatus		1 ♀	1 ♀			
Araneus	cavaticus		1 imm.				
Araneus	diadematus						1 ♀
Araneus	Gadus						1 ♂
Araneus	marmoreus						1 ♀
Araneus	miniatus						1 ♀
Araneus	partitus				2 ♀		
Araneus	thaddeus	1 ♂	1 ♀				1 ♀
Araneus	trifolium						1 penult. ♀
Argiope	aurantia			4 ♀ 2 ♂			
Argiope	trifasciata			5 ♀ 11 ♂			1 ♂
Cyclosa	turbinata			1 ♀			1 ♀
Eustala	anastera			9 ♀ 1 ♂	1 ♀		
Eustala	emertoni						1 ♀
Mangora	maculata					4 ♀	
Micrathena	sagittata					3 ♀ 6 ♂	
Neoscona	arabesca	5 ♀	25 ♀ 4 ♂	3 ♀ 1 ♂	25 ♀ 6 ♂	1 ♀ 1 ♂	2 ♀ 1 ♂
No id	sp. B					1 ♀	1 ♀ 1 ♂
Atypidae (Purseweb spiders)							
Sphodros	niger					1 ♂	1 ♂
Clubionidae (Running spiders)							
Clubiona	abbotii	4 ♀		1 ♂		1 ♀	1 ♂
Clubiona	kastoni		1 ♀				
Clubiona	maritima						1 ♂
Clubiona	johnsoni						2 ♀
Elaver	excepta		3 ♀ 1 ♂	1 ♀	2 ♂	1 ♀ 2 ♂	1 ♀ 2 ♂
Corinnidae (Ant mimics)							
Castianeira	longipalpa	1 ♂	1 ♀	1 ♂	1 ♂	15 ♀ 10 ♂	1 ♀ 1 ♂
Castianeira	trilineata				1 ♀ 1 ♂		
Phrurorotimpus	alarius		1 ♀ 6 ♂	1 ♂	1 ♀	2 ♀ 1 ♂	
Phrurorotimpus	borealis		1 ♂	3 ♂			

Phrurotimpus	sp. D			1 ♂			
Scotinella	divesta	1 ♀	1 ♀				
Scotinella	minnetonka				1 ♀		
Scotinella	pugnata		1 ♂		1 ♂	1 ♀ 1 ♂	1 ♀ 1 ♂
Scotinella	sp. B	1 ♀					
Trachelas	pacificas						1 ♂
Dictynidae							
Cicurina	arcuata		1 ♀				
Dictyna	sp. A					1 ♀	
Dictyna	sp. B					15 imm.	1 pent, 2 imm.
Lathys	pallida	7 ♀					
Dysderidae (Pillbug hunter)							
Dysdera	crocata						1 ♀ 1 ♂
Gnaphosidae (Running spiders)							
Callilepis	pluto		1 ♂				
Cesonia	bilineata			1 imm.			1 imm.
Drassodes	neglectus			1 ♂			
Drassyllus	creolus			1 ♂			
Drassyllus	aprilinus				1 ♀		
Haplodrassus	signifer			5 ♂	1 ♂	1 ♂	
No id	sp. D			1 ♂			
Nodocion	eclecticus			1 ♂			
Sergiolus	capulatus			1 imm.		3 ♂	
Zelotes	duplex		1 ♀ 8 ♂	1 ♂	2 ♀	1 ♀ 4 ♂	
Zelotes	fratis	2 ♀	1 ♀	1 ♀	1 ♀		
Zelotes	hentzi	1 ♂	1 ♂		1 ♂	1 ♂	
Hahniidae							
Neoantistea	agilis					1 ♀ 1 ♂	
Linyphiidae (Sheetweb weavers)							
Agyneta	sp. A				3 ♂		
Bathyphantes	pallidus				3 ♀ 4 ♂		
Bathyphantes	reprobus						1 ♀
Ceraticelus	bulbosus		1 ♂			5 ♀ 7 ♂	
Ceraticelus	sp. TA						1 ♀
Ceratinella	sp. A					1 ♀	
Ceratinopsis	nigriceps						1 ♀
Erigone	dentosa						1 ♂
Florinda	coccinea				2 ♀		
Grammonota	capitata			1 ♂			
Grammonota	sp. A		1 ♂				
Grammonota	sp. B						4 ♀ 3 ♂
Grammonota	pictilis		1 ♀				1 ♀
		1 penult.					
Hypselistes	florens	♂	6 ♀		1 ♀		
Macrargus	multesimus		2 ♂		2 ♀	1 ♂	
Maso	Morpho sp. A		2 ♀				
Maso	sp. B				2 ♀		
Nerienne	clathrata						1 ♀
No id	sp. A					1 ♀	
No id	sp. AA		1 ♀				
No id	sp. AB		1 ♀				
No id	sp. AC		1 ♂				
No id	sp. AD		2 imm.				

No id	sp. C		2 ♀				
No id	sp. D		4 ♀				
No id	sp. K			1 ♂			
No id	sp. P				1 ♀		1 ♀
No id	sp. R				1 ♂		
No id	sp. S		2 ♀			1 ♀	
No id	sp. T						1 ♂
No id	sp. U					2 ♀	
No id	sp. W		1 ♀	1 ♀			
No id	sp. X			1 ♀	1 ♀		
No id	sp. Y		1 ♂				
Pocadicnemis	americana			2 ♂			
Tennesseellum	formicum						2 ♂
Walckenaeria	atrotibialis					2 ♂	
Walckenaeria	digitata			1 ♀			
Walckenaeria	sp. A						1 ♀ 1 ♂
Liocranidae (Running spiders)							
Agroeca	pratensis		1 ♀				1 ♂
Agroeca	ornata						1 ♀
Lycosidae (Wolf spiders)							
Allocosa	sublata	1 ♂				4 ♂	
Arctosa	littoralis						1 ♀
Arctosa	rubicunda		1 ♀				
Geolycosa	domiflex	1 ♀ 21 ♂					
Hogna	carolinensis						1 ♀
Hogna	frondicola		5 ♂	6 ♂		1 ♂	
Hogna	helluo		4 ♀ 1 ♂	2 ♀ 1 ♂	2 ♀ 1 ♂	1 ♂	
Hogna	sp. C			1 ♀			
Paradosa	distincta			9 ♂	1 ♀ 4 ♂	7 ♂	
Paradosa	moesta		4 ♀ 11 ♂				
Paradosa	milvina						1 ♂
Paradosa	sp. A	2 ♀	3 ♀				
Paradosa	saxatilis	2 ♀		1 ♀ 2 ♂			
Pirata	canadensis					4 ♂	
Pirata	cantralli						1 ♀
Pirata	insularis					1 ♀	
Pirata	piraticus						1 ♂
						1 penult.	
Rabidosa	rabida			1 ♀	♀		
Schizocosa	avida						1 imm.
Schizocosa	communis	5 ♂	1 ♀	12 ♀ 11 ♂			
Schizocosa	crassipalpata			2 ♀ 2 ♂	1 ♂	1 ♂	
Trabeops	aurantiacus		2 ♀ 4 ♂		2 ♂		
Trebacosa	marxi		3 ♂			4 ♂	
Trochosa	terricola		1 ♀ 1 ♂				
Varacosa	shenandoa			1 ♀			1 ♂
Mimetidae (Pirate spiders)							
Mimetus	notius						1 ♂
Miturgidae							
Cheiracanthium	mildei						1 ♀ 1 ♂
Oxyopidae (Lynx spiders)							
Oxyopes	salticus		1 ♀				
Oxyopes	scalaris		2 ♀				
Philodromidae (Philodromid crab spiders)							

Philodromus	imbecillus				1 ♀			
Philodromus	placidus		1 ♀	1 penult. ♂	1 ♀			
Thanatus	formicinus							1 ♂
Thanatus	sp. A		1 ♀	1 penult. ♀				
Tibellus	oblongus	4♀ 1♂						
Pholcidae (Cellar spiders)								
Pholcus	phalangioides							1 ♂
Pisauridae (Fishing spiders)								
Dolmedes	sp. A							2 imm.
Salticidae (Jumping spiders)								
Attidops	tibialis							1 ♀
Eris	militaris					2 ♂		1 ♀
Habronattus	sp. A							8 imm.
Hentzia	palmarum	1♀ 3♂	2♀ 3♂	1 ♂				11♀ 12♂
Maevia	inclemens		1 ♂	2♀ 1♂				1 ♀
Marpissa	lineata					1 ♂		
Neon	nellii				1 ♂			
No id	sp. D		4 imm.					2 imm.
No id	sp. E							3 imm.
No id	sp. F							1 ♀
Pelegrina	flavipes							4♀ 3♂
Pelegrina	montana				1 ♀			1 ♀
Pelegrina	proterva		2♀ 1♂		1 ♀	5♀ 1♂		1♀ 12♂
Phidippus	audax							2 imm.
Phidippus	cardinalis	1 ♀		2♀ 1♂				1♀ 1♂
Phidippus	clarus		3 ♂					
Phidippus	sp. B				1 ♂	2 ♂		1 ♂
Platycryptus	undatus							1♀ 2♂
Synemosyna	formica							1 ♂
Zygoballus	rufipes							2 ♀
Scytodidae								
Scytodes	thoracica							2 imm.
Segestriidae								
Ariadna	bicolor							2 ♂
Tetragnathidae (Long-jawed orb weavers)								
Leucauge	venusta		1 ♀			1 ♀		2 ♀
Tetragnatha	caudata							3 imm.
Tetragnatha	elongata					1 ♀		
Tetragnatha	guatemalensis							1 ♂
Tetragnatha	laboriosa	1 ♀		3 ♂	1♀ 1♂			1 ♀
Tetragnatha	versicolor					1 ♂		
Tetragnatha	viridis							1 penult. ♂
Theridiidae (Cobweb weavers)								
Achaearanea	globosa		1 ♀					
Achaearanea	sp. B		1 ♀					
Achaearanea	tepidariorum							2♀ 5♂
Argyrodes	trigonum							1 ♀
Dipoena	sp. A				1 ♀	2 ♀		
Dipoena	sp. B					1 ♂		
Emertonella	emertoni		1 ♂					
Enoplognatha	ovata							3♀ 1♂
Euryopis	funbris		3 ♂		1 ♀	1 ♀		
Euryopis	gertschi		1♀ 5♂	1 ♂				

Latrodectus	mactans							1 ♀
No id	sp. B					3 ♀		
No id	sp. L		1 imm.					
No id	sp. N					1 ♀		
No id	sp. O		1 ♀					
No id	sp. P							1 ♂
Robertus	pumilis		1 ♂					
Steatoda	americana		2 ♂				2 ♂	
Steatoda	borealis							1 ♀
Steatoda	sp. A	1 ♀						
Theonoe	stridula			1 imm.				
Theridion	albidum						4 ♀	
Theridion	frondeum						1 ♀	
Theridion	lyricum				1 ♀		2 ♀	
Theridion	differens		1 ♂					1 imm.
Thymoites	unimaculatus						1 ♀	
Wamba	crispulus		1 ♂					
Thomisidae (Crab spiders)								
Misumena	sp. A							1 imm.
Misumenoides	formosipes							1 ♀ 1 ♂
Ozyptila	conspurcata	1 ♂	3 ♂	2 ♂	2 ♂	2 ♂		
Ozyptila	practicola							1 penult. ♀
	sincera							
Ozyptila	canadensis		3 ♀	1 ♂	2 ♀	1 ♀		
Xysticus	alboniger							1 ♀
Xysticus	ferox	2 ♀	5 ♂	1 ♀ 1 ♂		1 ♂		
Xysticus	fratenus		1 ♂			1 ♀ 2 ♂		
			1 penult.					
Xysticus	funestus		♀		1 ♂			3 ♀ 1 ♂
Xysticus	gulosus			1 ♂				
Xysticus	luctans		1 ♂					
Xysticus	sp. E			1 ♂				
				penult: 1 ♀				
Xysticus	pellax			1 ♂	1 ♂			
Xysticus	triguttatus							1 ♀
No id								
			1 penult.					
No id	sp. A	♂			1 penult. ♂			
Total # species		26	70	54	46	52	91	
Total # specimens (incl. imm. and penult.)		81	190	146	105	158	193	

Appendix B

Emerton's 1930 species list

Family	Modern Genus	Modern species	Found in 2006?	
Theridiidae	Achaearanea	tepidariorum	Yes	
	Theridion	differens	Yes	
	Theridion	murarium		
	Theridion	glaucescens		
	Theridion	frondeum	Yes	
	Wamba	crispulus	Yes	
	Thymoites	unimaculatum	Yes	
	Steatoda	borealis	Yes	
	Enoplognatha	marmorata		
	Crustulina	guttata		
	Crustulina	sticta		
	Dipoena	nigra		
	Theridula	opulenta		
	Mimitidae	Mimetus	sylllepsicus	
	Pholcidae	Pholcus	phalangioides	Yes
	Linyphiidae	Ceraticelus	fissiceps	
Ceraticelus		alticeps		
Ceraticelus		emertoni		
Ceraticelus		brunnea		
Ceratinopsis		formosa		
Ceratinella		parvula		
Ceratiopsis		atolma OR nigripalpis		
Grammonota		pictilis	Yes	
Grammonota		capitata	Yes	
Grammonota		inornata		
Walckenaeria		auranticeps		
Walckenaeria		communis		
Walckenaeria		spiralis		
Erigone		autumnalis		
Erigone		dentigera		
Erigone		atra		
Eridantes		erigonoides		
Pocadicnemis		pumila		
Ceratinops		crenatus		
Satlatlas		arenarius		
Eperigone		tenuipalpis		
Eperigone		trilobata		
Eperigone		maculata		
Collinsia		plumosa		
Microneta		viaria		
Meioneta		micaria		
Meioneta		simplex		
Lepthyphantes		minutus		
Neriere		clathrata	Yes	
Neriere		variabilis		
Frontinella		communis		
Araneidae		Larinioides	sclopetarius	

	Araneus	trifolium	Yes
	Araneus	marmoreus	Yes
	Araneus	thaddeus	Yes
	Neoscona	arabesca	Yes
	Neoscona	pratensis	
	Araneus	juniperi	
	Araneus	miniatus	Yes
	Mangora	placida	
	Mangora	gibberosa	
	Eustala	anastera	Yes
	Acanthepeira	stellata	Yes
	Leucauge	venusta	Yes
	Zygiella	x-notata	
	Hypsosinga	pygmaea	
	Larinia	borealis	
	Argiope	trifasciata kauaiensis	Yes
	Argiope	aurantia	Yes
Theridosomatidae	Theridiosoma	gemmosum	
Tetragnathidae	Tetragnatha	labriosa	Yes
	Tetragnatha	straminea	
	Tetragnatha	pinicola	
	Tetragnatha	pallescens	
	Tetragnatha	caudata	Yes
	Pachygnatha	tristriata	
	Glenognatha	foxi	
Dictynidae	Emblyna	annulipes	
	Dictyna	sublata	
	Emblyna	angulata	
	Callobius	bennetti	
	Argenna	obesa	
	Cicurina	arcuata	Yes
Agelenidae	Agelenopsis	naevia	
	Tegenaria	domestica	Yes
Hahniidae	Neoantistea	agilis	Yes
	Hahnia	cinerea	
	Antistea	brunnea	
Lycosidae	Hogna	helluo	Yes
	Hogna	frondicola	Yes
	Schizocosa	avida	Yes
	Trochosa	terricola	Yes
	Arctosa	littoralis	Yes
	Geolycosa	turricola	
	Geolycosa	pikei	
	Allocosa	funerea	
	Schizocosa	bilineata	
	Hogna	carolinensis	
	Pardosa	moesta	Yes
	Pardosa	littoralis	
	Pardosa	milvina	Yes
	Trabeops	aurantiacus	Yes
	Pirata	aspirans	

	Trebacosa	marxi	Yes
	Pirata	piraticus	Yes
	Pirata	sylvestrus OR piraticus	
Oxyopidae	Oxyopes	scalaris	Yes
Dysderidae	Dysdera	crocata	Yes
Segestriidae	Ariadna	bicolor	Yes
Gnaphosidae	Gnaphosa	muscorum	
	Gnaphosa	parvula	
	Haplodrassus	hiemalis	
	Zelotes	ater	No modern name
	Zelotes	depressa	No modern name
	Cesonia	bilineata	Yes
	Sergiolus	capulatus	Yes
	Sergiolus	unimaculatus	
	Agroeca	pratensis	Yes
	Agroeca	ornata	Yes
	Unknown species		
Anyphaenidae	Anyphaena	celer	
	Hibana	gracilis	
	Unknown species		
Corinnidae	Phrurolithus	alarius	Yes
	Scotinella	pugnata	Yes
	Micaria	longipes	
Zoridae	Zora	spinimana	
Corinnidae	Castianeira	ingulata	
	Castianeira	crocata	
	Cheiracanthium	inclusum	
	Clubiona	pallens	No modern name
	Clubiona	maritima	Yes
	Clubiona	littoralis	
	Clubiona	abboti	Yes
	Clubiona	saltitans	
Thomisidae	Xysticus	ferox	Yes
	Xysticus	gulosus	Yes
	Xysticus	punctatus	
	Xysticus	funestus	Yes
	Xysticus	luctans	Yes
	Xysticus	trigutattus	Yes
	Xysticus	gramineus	No modern name
	Xysticus	discursans	
	Bassaniana	versicolor	
	Ozyptila	conspurcata	Yes
	Xysticus	alboniger	Yes
	Misumenops	oblongus	
	Misumenops	asperatus	
	Misumenoides	formosipes	Yes
	Misumena	vatia	
Philodromidae	Philodromus	imbecillus	Yes
	Philodromus	laticeps	
	Philodromus	placidus	Yes
	Philodromus	marxi	

	Ebo	latithorax	
	Tibellus	oblongus	Yes
	Thanatus	striatus	
Salticidae	Phidippus	insignarius	
	Phidippus	cardinalis	Yes
	Phidippus	princeps	
	Phidippus	clarus	
	Pelegrina	proterva	Yes
	Eris	militaris	Yes
	Zygoballus	nervosus	
	Zygoballus	rufipes	Yes
	Hentzia	palmarum	Yes
	Marpissa	pikei	
	Salticus	scenicus	
	Platycryptus	undatus	Yes
	Neon	nelli	Yes
	Habronattus	agilis	
	Habronattus	borealis	
	Synemosyna	formica	Yes
	Sitticus	floricola palustris	
	Sitticus	striatus	
	Phlegra	hentzi	
	Agassa	cyanea	

Appendix C.

Tuckernuck Species List

Asterisk (*) indicates fully identified species not yet captured on Nantucket

Number and Sex			Number and Sex		
Agelenidae			Lycosidae		
Agelenopsis	emertoni	1 ♂	Hogna	helluo	1 ♀
Agelenopsis	potteri	4 ♀	Paradosa	distincta	1 ♀
Araneidae			Rabidoso	rabida	1 penult. ♀
Acanthepeira	stellata	6 imm.	Schizocosa	communis	1 ♀
Araneus	bicentenarius	1 imm.	Schizocosa	ocreat*	2 ♀
Araneus	trifolium	1 ♂	Trebacosa	marxi	1 ♀
Argiope	aurantia	1 penult. ♀	Philodromidae		
Argiope	trifasciata	2 ♂	Thanatus	sp. A	4 imm.
Larinoides	cornutus	5 ♀	Salticidae		
Micrathena	sagittata	1 ♀	Admestina	wheeleri*	1 ♂
Neoscona	arabesca	6 ♀	Hentzia	palmarum	4 ♀, 2 ♂
No id	sp. A	7 imm.	Neon	nellii	1 ♀
No id	sp. B	1 imm.	No id	sp. D	1 imm.
Atypidae			Pelegrina	proterva	2 ♀
Sphodros	sp. TA	2 ♀	Sassacus	sp. A	1 imm.
Clubionidae			Zygoballus	rufipes	1 ♀, 2 ♂
Elaver	excepta	1 ♂	Tetragnathidae		
Dictynidae			Leucauge	venusta	2 ♀, 1 ♂
Cicurina	arcuata	1 ♀	Theridiidae		
Dictyna	sp. A	3 imm.	Achaearanea	tepidariorum	2 ♀
Dictyna	sp. B	1 imm.	Euryopis	funebrus	1 ♂
Gnaphosidae			No id	sp. TB	1 ♂
Cesonia	bilineata	1 imm.	No id	sp. TC	5 ♀
Linyphiidae			Phoroncidia	americana*	1 ♂
Bathyphantes	pallidus	1 ♂	Steatoda	borealis	1 ♀
Ceraticelus	bulbosus	5 ♀	Steatoda	sp. TA	2 imm.
Ceraticelus	sp. TA	22 ♀, 12 ♂	Theridion	lyricum	1 ♀
Ceraticelus	silus*	1 ♂	Theridion	sp. B	2 ♀
Grammonota	capitata	1 ♂	Thymoites	sp. A	2 ♀
Grammonota	maritima*	1 ♂	Tidarren	sp. TA	2 ♀
No id	sp. C	2 ♀	Wamba	congener*	1 ♂
No id	sp. TB	Hermaphrodite?	Thomisidae		
			Misumenoides	formosipes	3 ♂

No id	sp. TC	1 ♀	Xysticus	funestus	1 ♀, 1 ♂
Number of specimens represented = 147					
Total number of species = 56					

Appendix D
Muskget Species List

Asterisk (*) indicates fully identified species not yet captured on Nantucket

Number and Sex			Number and Sex		
Agelenidae			Salticidae		
Agelenopsis	emertoni	1 ♀, 1 ♂	Hentzia	palmarum	3 ♀, 2 ♂
Anyphaenidae			Pelegrina	flavipes	1 ♀
Hibana	sp. A	1 ♀	Salticus	scenicus	1 ♀
Araneidae			Tetragnathidae		
Acanthepeira	stellata	18 imm.	Tetragnatha	caudata	7 ♀, 3 ♂
Araneus	trifolium	1 ♂	Tetragnatha	laboriosa	5 ♀
Argiope	trifasciata	1 ♀	Tetragnatha	vermiformis	2 ♂
Eustala	emertoni	1 ♀	Theridiidae		
Neoscona	arabesca	6 ♀, 1 ♂	Achaeearanea	tepidariorum	5 ♀, 2 ♂
Clubionidae			Thomisidae		
Clubiona	pikei	8 ♀	Misumenoides	formosipes	1 ♀, 2 ♂
Corinnidae			Xysticus	ferox	1 ♀
Phruronellus	formica	4 ♀, 3 ♂	Xysticus	triguttatus	2 ♀
Gnaphosidae					
Zelotes	hentzi	1 ♂			
Linyphiidae					
Ceratinopsis	sp. A	1 ♂			
Grammonota	inornata	1 ♀, 1 ♂			
Grammonota	sp. C	1 ♀			
Hypselistes	florens	3 imm.			
No id	sp. AE	2 ♀			
Lycosidae					
Arctosa	littoralis	1 ♀, 1 penult. ♂			
Hogna	sp. A	1 ♀			
Pirata	insularis	1 ♀, 1 ♂			
Schizocosa	avida	1 ♀			
Philodromidae					
Philodromus	imbecillus	1 ♀			
Tibellus	oblongus	2 ♀, 2 ♂			
Pholcidae					
Pholcus	phalangioides	9 ♀, 5 ♂			
Number of specimens represented = 118					
Total number of species = 32					

